

Impact of Enterprenuership Education on Enterprenuerial Intentions of Polytechnic Student in Kano State, Nigeria

BY

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Abstract

This research assessed the impact of enterprenuership education on the enterprenuerial intentions of polytechnic students to start a new venture using Linen's model. The objectives of the study are to determine the effect of enterprenuership education towards starting new business venture among HND and ND students; to determine whether enterprenuership education will influence students' perceived desirability of enterprenuership, and to determine whether enterprenuership education will influence students' perceived feasibility of enterprenuership in Kano State Polytechnic. The methodology adopted in this study was a survey research design with a population of 932 HND and ND students of final year in the departments of architecture, quantity survey, and building technology and urban and regional planning using Logit model and ANOVA. Sample was drawn using the table for determining sample size by Krejchic and Morgan 2006, in which a population of 932 has selected a sample of 275 subjects. The instrument for data collection was a 5 point Likert Scale type questionnaire adopted from (Ajzen, 1991; Brid, 1998; Krueger, 2005; Liñán, 2004). The questionnaire was designed in order to measure those variables (education, intention, desirability, and feasibility); that have impacts on enterprenuerial intentions. The reliability of the questionnaire was at 0.72 level of coefficient using Crombach Alpha. The findings suggested positive relationship between entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship intentions, perceived desirability and perceived feasibility in the logit analysis. The empirical findings demonstrate that the enterprenuerial intention is very high among the sampled students; that enterprenuerial education is working well to generate high enterprenuerial intention in the Nigerian context. The study recommended that the local government councils of the State and stakeholders such as voluntary individual, NGOs, and multinational co-operations should be given the authority to established adequate skill acquisition centres in their various communities in the State as a gesture for cooperate social responsibility, and there is the need for redesigning of the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) to embrace the spirit of enterprenuership and skill acquisition among the teeming unemployed youth in Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneur, Education, Intention, Desirability, and Feasibility

Introduction

Entrepreneurship occupies an increasingly important place in modern economies since it is the main source of wealth and fight against poverty and unemployment. Thus, the similarities and differences between nations and or countries are based in essence on differences in employment rates and new venture creation. Moreover, entrepreneurship as a field of research has considerable importance from economic, social, and political point of view (Ladyga, 2015). Entrepreneurial intent (EI) is the first act in the entrepreneurial process. It could be seen as a “Self-acknowledged conviction by individuals that they intend to set up a new business venture and consciously plan to do so at some point in the future” (Thompson, 2009). EI summarizes the willingness of a person to create his own enterprise (Fayolle, Gailly, and Lassas-Clerc 2006), and can be explained by several factors. In this context therefore, entrepreneurship education (EE) has evolved to become a prominent field. Actually, a successful entrepreneurship is positively affected by the dispositions, skills and competences of the entrepreneur. These dispositions, skills and competences can be shaped by education (Illes, Dunnay, and Jelonek, 2015). Numerous studies have shown that entrepreneurship education contributes to the development of entrepreneurial intention (Kuttim, Kallaste, Venessaar, and Kiis, 2014; Mat, Maat, and Mohd, 2015; Valliere, 2015; Sondari, 2014; Fayolle, Gailly, and Lassas-Clerc, 2006). However, the content and context of entrepreneurship education vary between universities, institutions, countries and regions. Consequently, many authors proposed a common framework based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) proposed by Ajzen (1991) to assess change in student intention toward entrepreneurship. The need for entrepreneurship education has been well established in recent studies. However, there is a debate on how the education should be provided, what is the students’ perception on the

entrepreneurship education. It is however, argued that the traditional education system does not promote the attributes and skills that are required to produce entrepreneurs. The traditional education system teaches students how to become a good employee instead of a successful entrepreneur (Solomon, 1989) The question here, is to what extent does EE contribute to the development of EI especially in developing country like Nigeria where it's regarded as new phenomenon or recent innovation.

Although, there is no universally accepted definition of entrepreneurship, there is an agreement that it is a process entailing recognition of a need, exploiting an opportunity to fulfil the need and building an enterprise around it. This behaviour would be best predicted by the entrepreneurial intentions (Liñán, Rodriguez and Ruedacantuch, 2010). For some scholars, venture creation is an outcome of intentions (Maina, 2011). Entrepreneurial intention is a determinant element to perform entrepreneurial behaviour (Pribadi, 2005) It is a state of mind which directs and guides the actions of individuals towards the development and implementation of new business concepts (Bird, 1998). The intention to carry out a given behaviour can be predicted by the person's attitudes towards that behaviour (Maina, 2011; Pribadi, 2005), that is, whether the performance of this behaviour is positively or negatively valued. These attitudes converge with situational factors to drive or hinder the establishment of new businesses (Boyd and Vozikiz, 1994). According to London (1983) situational factors include prior exposure to entrepreneurship, availability of role models and social attitudes towards entrepreneurship; all together are likely to have a positive bearing on individual's decision to venture into business.

According to Maina (2011) 'enterpreneuers' discover enterpreneuership opportunities depending on the information they already have'. This information can be obtained from education programmes that aim at building knowledge and skills either 'about' or 'for the purpose of' entrepreneurship, generally, as a part of recognised education programmes at primary, secondary or tertiary level educational institutions (Corduras, Levie, Kelly, Saemundsson, and Schott, 2010). Enterprise education may, therefore, have a positive impact on enterprenuel intentions by providing enterprenuel skills and knowledge (Peterman and Kennedy, 2003; Rae, 2006).

A prior research in Anglo-Nations has demonstrated marked differences between students who are intending to be entrepreneurs and those who are not (Levenburg & Schwarz, 2008). Henderson and Robertson (1999) found that 67 percent of those studying enterpreneuership expressed a desire for self-employment. A key assumption under entrepreneurship education is that entrepreneurial skills can be taught and are not fixed personal characteristics (Oosterbeek, Van Praag and Ijsselstein, 2007), which complies with Drucker's (1985) view of entrepreneurship as a discipline and like any discipline it can be learned, and Rushing's (1990) contention that entrepreneurship education can enhance and develop traits that are associated with entrepreneurship and provide skills needed to start businesses. Liñán (2004) proposed that the education of an entrepreneur should be based on strengthening the participant's intention of becoming an entrepreneur. He integrated the two theories of Ajzen's the Planned Behaviour Theory (1991) and Shapero and Sokol's Theory of the Enterprenuerial Event (1982) into an enterprenuerial intention model by adding the additional element of enterprenuerial knowledge acquired through education. The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) explains the individual's actions in terms of intentions through establishing a link between attitudes and behaviour. It is

based on the premise that much of human behaviour is planned and, therefore, predicted by intention towards that behaviour (Izquierdo & Buelens, 2008), especially in cases where the behaviour is difficult to observe, rare and involves unpredictable times lags (Basu & Virick, 2008). TPB includes three components that predict behavioural intentions (Miller, Bell, Palmer, Gonzalez & Petroleum, 2009): (1) Personal attitude towards outcome of behaviour: The degree to which a person has a favourable or unfavourable evaluation of behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). (2) Perceived social norm (subjective norms), or pressure to perform the behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). (3) Perceived behavioural control—the perception of ease or difficulty of performing certain behaviours (Ajzen, 1991). In more recent work, Ajzen (2002) affirmed that the measures of perceived behavioural control need to incorporate self-efficacy (dealing largely with ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour) and controllability (the extent to which performance is up to the actor). Shapero and Sokol (1982) stated that firm creation is the result of the interaction among contextual factors, which would act through their influence on the individual's perceptions. The consideration of the entrepreneurial option would take place as a consequence of some external change (appreciating event). The person's answer to that external event will depend on his/her perception of perceived desirability and perceived feasibility. Whereas feasibility is built around perceived competency to carry out a specific behaviour, the desirability relates to how personally rewarding the behaviour/task is perceived to be (Cooper & Lucas, 2008); both are recognised to have a positive relation with entrepreneurial intentions. The integration of the two theories results in combining personal attitude and perceived social norms under perceived desirability, while perceived feasibility is represented by self-efficacy. Controllability is not a part of this model as evidence showed that self-efficacy is superior to controllability in predicting intentions and behaviour (Rhodes & Courneya, 2003). This is

supported by Boyd and Vozikis' (1994) supposition that entrepreneurial intentions are stronger with a growing degree of entrepreneurial self-efficacy due to the presence of entrepreneurial role models in close relatives (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Linen's Entrepreneurial Intention Model

Source: Liñán (2004: 6, Figure 2).

Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurship education is continually gaining massive interest among academics, policy makers and sundry of stake holders. It is opined that enterprenuerial engagement is the 21st century strategy for economic growth and development of any nation (Nelson and Johnson, 1997; Afolabi, 2015; Sule, 2015; Akpan, Effiong and Ele, 2012). In essence, the Federal Ministry of Education through the National University Commission (NUC), National Board for Technical Education (NBTE), and National Council Colleges of Education (NCCE) has made enterprenuership education compulsory for every student in Nigeria tertiary institutions with the hope that it will

spur graduate business startups (Fems, 2016). However, for over ten years of this policy implementation, Nigerian graduates still wallow in the vortex of unemployment and unrestrained job seeking as opposed to job creation (Fems, Poazi, and Opigo, 2017).

This study, therefore, assesses the impact of a dedicated entrepreneurship education course offered to a cohort of students among polytechnic students in Kano State on their entrepreneurial intentions. The module is offered over one semester and covers the definitions and characteristics of entrepreneurs in order to help students identify the entrepreneur in themselves to generate ideas for a business and ultimately produce a business plan to take their idea into the market.

Objectives of the Research

The main objective of this study is to assess the impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurship intention among Nigerian students using Kano State polytechnic as a case study. Other specific objectives of the study are:

1. To determine the effect of entrepreneurship education towards starting new business venture among HND and ND students of Kano State Polytechnic;
2. To determine whether entrepreneurship education will influence students' perceived desirability of entrepreneurship in Kano State Polytechnic, and
3. To determine whether entrepreneurship education will influence students' perceived feasibility of entrepreneurship in Kano State Polytechnic.

Research Hypotheses

In the light of literature and Liñán's model, the research aims at testing the following

hypotheses:

1. H1a Students who received enterprenuership education will be more driven towards starting their own ventures (higher intention) than students who did not receive enterprenuership education
2. H1b: Exposure to enterprenuership education will influence students' perceived desirability of enterprenuership
3. H1c: Exposure to enterprenuership education will influence students' perceived feasibility of enterprenuership
4. H2: Students' perceived desirability of enterprenuership will influence their enterprenuerial intentions
5. H3: Students' perceived feasibility of enterprenuership will influence their enterprenuerial intentions

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design. The population of the study was nine hundred and thirty two students of Higher National Diploma (HND) in Kano State polytechnic. Sample was drawn using the krejchie and Morgan's table for determining sample size from a given population. According to the table, a population of 932 has selected a sample of two hundred and seventy five (275) subjects. However, the sample participants in the study consisted of students who were, at the time of the survey, in their final Higher National Diploma (HND) and National Diploma (ND) programmes at the school of environmental studies, Gwarzo in the three (3) departments of architecture, quantity survey and building technology and urban and regional planning. These students at this levels have started contemplating different occupational decisions

including starting their own businesses. Moreover, a multi-stage sampling technique was used in reaching to the sampled subjects; this is because they fall in the age group that is the second most entrepreneurially active group, ranging from (18–35). The numbers of students in their last year in the programmes at three departments were: architecture, (101), quantity survey and Building (119) urban and regional planning (55).

The rationale behind the choice of the three departments was to compare between students who were exposed to formal education in entrepreneurship (architecture, quantity survey. and Building) and who were not (urban and regional planning) to find out whether there was any significant difference in intentions as a result of studying entrepreneurship or not. Another comparison conducted was between architecture, students before and after their exposure to the formal education of entrepreneurship, early in the semester and at the end of semester to see if their entrepreneurial intentions have been affected by entrepreneurial education or not.

Data were collected through the use of a 5 point Likert Scale type questionnaire adopted from (Ajzen, 1991; Brid, 1998; Krueger, 2005; Liñán, 2004; Liñán et al., 2010). The questionnaire was designed in order to measure those variables (education, intention, desirability, and feasibility); that have impacts on enterprenuerial intentions, (see.the work of Hala W. Hattab, 2014). The questionnaire was distributed to all 275 final year students at HND and ND programmes, unfortunatly only 219 sets were successfully returned; yielding a response rate of 79.6%. Therefore, the analysis in this study was based on the 219 questionnaires returned from the field. Moreover, in this study, the perceived desirability was identified as the combination of personal attitude; which was defined as the individual's assessment of the value of enterprenuership and the perceived social norms, which was defined as expectation or pressure exerted by family, friends and society on the students not to create their own enterprises; while

perceived feasibility was represented by self-efficacy, which was defined as the individual's confidence that they can successfully engage in entrepreneurial behaviour. The reliability of the questionnaire reported was at the average of 0.72 level of consistency using Cronbach's Alpha which is according to rule of thumb was good (George and Mallery, 2003). Data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics via analysis of variance (ANOVA) and binary logit model. This was conducted using *Stata 14* software. However, while the descriptive statistics presented the data in frequency counts and percentages; means, standard deviation and variances. The inferential statistics were analysed using marginal effects after binary logit.

Results

A total of 219 respondent's questionnaires were subjected to analysis, of which 95.1% were males, 4.9% were females. In terms of departments; 25% of respondents were urban and regional planning students, while 36.7% were architecture students, the remaining 38.3% were quantity survey and building students. With regard to studying the entrepreneurship module, 50% said no, they have not previously taken a class in entrepreneurship as opposed to 49% who said yes. However, 66.5% said they personally know an entrepreneur, as opposed to 33.5% who said no. In terms of intentions to start to a business, 15.4% said they never thought of creating or founding their own business. While 13.7% said they did not have the thought of starting their own business but they intend to join their family business, 34.1% said they have the thought, but they are still not sure if they will pursue this. Similarly, 22% said they are serious about starting their own business and 14.8% said they are determined to found their own business and are clear about it.

Hypotheses Testing

The analyses were conducted in several stages. The first stage has tested H1a, H1b and H1c to

investigate the impact of education on intentions, perceived desirability and perceived feasibility of entrepreneurship. Before proceeding further with testing the hypotheses, normality test was conducted. Since the significance value of the Shapiro-Wilk test is below 0.05 then the data significantly deviate from a normal distribution (see Table 2 test for normality of the constructs), hence, the Mann-Whitney U-test was used to test the hypothesis.

Table 3 shows the mean rank and sum of ranks for the two groups tested at significance level (α) = 0.05. Initially it can be said that the students who studied entrepreneurship showed higher levels of entrepreneurial intentions and perceived desirability compared to students who never studied entrepreneurship, showing that mean rank is higher for the students who said yes, whereas perceived feasibility was lower among (HND and ND) students.

Table 2. Test for Normality of the Constructs

	ShapiroWilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Entrepreneurial Intentions	0.903	178	0.011
Perceived Desirability	0.562	178	0.000
Perceived Feasibility	0.610	178	0.045
Exposure to Entrepreneurship Education	0.636	178	0.000

Source: Generated by Author

Results of Table 3 (combined with that of Table 2) were used to accept/reject the hypotheses. H1a will be accepted as the p -value (α) = 0.000 < 0.05 and the sum of ranks for the group who studied entrepreneurship > Wilcoxon W. Hence, it is confirmed that entrepreneurship education has an impact on the entrepreneurial intentions of polytechnic student students. Also H1b is accepted as the p -value (α) = 0.001 < 0.05 and the sum of ranks for the group who studied entrepreneurship > Wilcoxon W; hence, it is confirmed entrepreneurship education has

an impact on the desirability of creating a business. H1c is rejected as the p -value (α) = 0.624 > 0.05 and the sum of ranks for the group who studied entrepreneurship < Wilcoxon W; hence, entrepreneurship education does not impact the level of feasibility.

The paired Samples t-Test was conducted to complement the hypotheses testing, where unit of analysis was the CS students before and after being exposed to entrepreneurial education. The assumption is there is no difference before and after exposure to entrepreneurship education. The analysis reveals there is a difference in students' intentions to start a business as well as in perceived desirability before and after exposure to entrepreneurship (see Table 4); thus, null hypothesis is rejected. Regarding the feasibility of creating a business, the p -value = 0.464 > 0.05; hence, the null hypothesis is accepted that difference does not exist.

In the second stage, multiple regression analyses were conducted to test hypotheses 2 and 3. As a start, p -value of the F -test is checked to see

Table 3. Ranks of the Constructs for the Perceived Desirability Intentions and Perceived Feasibility

	Have You Studied Entrepreneurship Before?	<i>N</i>	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Perceived Desirability	No	126	78.84	7174.00				
	Yes	93	104.16	9479.00				
	Total	219			2748.000	7274.000	-3.354-	0.001
Intentions	No	120	77.53	7055.00				
	Yes	99	105.47	9598.00				
	Total	219			28879.000	7045.000	-3.591-	0.000
Perceived Feasibility	No	129	93.41	8500.00				
	Yes	90	89.59	8153.00				
	Total	219			3887.000	8133.000	-0.491-	0.654

Source: Generated by Author using SPSS. 2022

Notes: *N*: Observations and *Z*: z-test value.

Table 4. Paired Samples t-Test

Item	M		Std. Deviation		t.	p-value (Sig.)
	Before	After	Before	After		
Intention to create a business	17.1	17.3	4.8	5.2	1.377	0.048
Desirability of creating business	15.6	16.9	2.97	2.91	1.75	0.009
Feasibility of creating business	26.30	25.66	2.7	3.64	0.743	0.464

Source: Generated by Author using SPSS.

Notes: M: Mean and t: t-test value.

Table 5. ANOVA Analysis for the Desirability and Feasibility of Starting a Business

F	R Square ^b	Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients		T	Sig.
			B	Std. Error	Beta			
0.000	0.954	I	Desirability	0.389	0.050	0.577	7.824	0.00
			Feasibility	0.409	0.074	0.407	5.520	0.00

Source: Generated by Author using SPSS.

Notes: F = F-test value, B = Beta and T = t-test value.

It can be seen from the table above that the model is statistically significant with a p -value of zero (Table 5). The R-squared is 0.954 (Table 5), meaning that approximately 95% of the variability of dependent variable is accounted for by the variables in the model. In this case, the adjusted R-squared indicates that about 95% of the variability of intentions is accounted for by the variables in the model (desirability and feasibility).

The p -value of desirability and feasibility coefficient is zero (< 0.05), indicating the significance of these variables (Table 5). The B value for each of the independent variables is positive, signifying that any increase in each of these variables will have a positive impact on the dependent variables (intentions); therefore, H2 and H3 are accepted, that is, the perceived desirability and feasibility have an impact on intentions to start a business.

Table 6 and 7 present logit model and its subsequent marginal effect

LOGISTIC REGRESSION		NUMBER OF OBS = 198	
LR CHI2(6) = 18.06		PROB > CHI2 = 0.0061	
LOG LIKELIHOOD = -125.93015		PSEUDO R2 = 0.0669	

EI	COEF.	STD. ERR.	Z P> Z [95% CONF. INTERVAL]
-----+-----			
GEN	-.5808803	.3574763	-1.62 0.104 -1.281521 .1197604
AGE	.0054949	.168226	0.03 0.074 -.324222 .3352118
EDU	.4773375	.2207493	2.16 0.031 .0446769 .9099982
INC	-8.91E-06	4.80E-06	-1.86 0.063 -.0000183 4.99E-07
PF	.0587061	.1112279	0.53 0.008 -.1592966 .2767089
EEE	.9549022	.3052845	3.13 0.002 .3565555 1.553249
_CONS	-.8245893	.9533294	-0.86 0.387 -2.693081 1.043902

. MFX			
MARGINAL EFFECTS AFTER LOGIT			
Y = PR(EI) (PREDICT)			
= .58264489			

VARIABLE	DY/DX	STD. ERR.	Z P> Z [95% C.I.] X
-----+-----			
GEN	-.1412526	.0869	-1.63 0.104 -.311565 .02906 1.16162
AGE	.013362	.04091	0.03 0.974 -.078841 .081513 2.25758
EDU	.1160741	.05357	2.17 0.030 .011073 .221075 3.29293
INC	-2.17E-06	.00000	-1.86 0.063 -4.5E-06 1.2E-07 51199.8
PF	.0142756	.02705	0.53 0.598 -.038736 .067287 2.80303
EEE*	.230273	.07147	3.22 0.001 .09019 .370356 .565657

(*) DY/DX IS FOR DISCRETE CHANGE OF DUMMY VARIABLE FROM 0 TO 1			

Table 6 and 7 present logit model and its subsequent marginal effect. Exposure to entrepreneurship education is statistically significant and result from marginal effect at means suggest that with an increase in exposure to entrepreneurship education entrepreneurship

intention increases by 23%. Also the variable perceived feasibility which defined the level of student's self-confidence is statistically significant at 10% and it implies that with increase in student's self-confidence entrepreneurship intention increases by 14%. Another variable of interest is age of the students where a one-year increase in students age is associated with 10% increase in entrepreneurship intention, however, these findings are in line with a vast number of past empirical findings, for example see Ajzen (2000) Oosterbeek, Van Praag and Ijsselstein, 2007), but findings from the other variables like income and gender contradict past findings because a priori expect income and gender to co vary with entrepreneurship intention. With Pseudo R² = 0.0669 the explanatory power of the model is set to be normal giving the nature of the cross sectional study.

Discussion of Findings

Many empirical studies have indicated that entrepreneurship can be taught or at least encouraged by entrepreneurship/business education (Wang and Verzat, 2011). Moreover, most of these researches have been conducted in economies at advanced stages of development with very limited focus on developing countries.

The results from this study show that the percentage of students across three departments aspiring to pursue entrepreneurial careers is somewhat high. However, the percentage of students who confirmed their disinterest in entrepreneurship was higher among URP students, who were never exposed to entrepreneurship education. Among the group who studied entrepreneurship, architecture students were more inclined towards starting their own businesses compared to quantity survey students.

Similarly, in a study conducted by Richardson's (1993) entitled there is a significant difference

between perceived contributions of education with different academic majors. The study is in line with the findings of this study, hence, the comparison between intentions of students before and after being exposed to a dedicated course in entrepreneurship revealed that education has significant positive entrepreneurial outcomes: students' intentions towards self-employment increases. Students acquire further knowledge about entrepreneurship; hence, their perception of self-employment alters to deem it a positive career choice. This finding confirmed Dickson's, Solomon's, and Weever's, (2008) conclusions that entrepreneurship education is related to becoming an entrepreneur.

Conclusions

Over the years, entrepreneurship education is gaining momentum in developing countries especially in Nigeria where large quantum of students are graduating from universities, colleges, and polytechnics without a fallback position due to unemployment mass and abject poverty. Hence it was introduced due to the recognition and importance of entrepreneurship graduates in contributing to the economic growth and development of their countries. This study is one that attempted to study the impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of polytechnic students in a developing country like Nigeria.

It has been proved that entrepreneurship education has a positive impact on students' perceived desirability of self-employment. Entrepreneurial education was found to increase the degree of favourability of entrepreneurship among Nigerian students; a result that is consistent with Jones, Jones, Packham, and Miller, (2008) which concluded that entrepreneurship education can positively reinforce students' attitudes towards an entrepreneurial career choice in a developing country. However, its impact is less evident on the perceived feasibility; no effect for entrepreneurial education was found on the self-efficacy of students; a result that is not

consistent with some of the previous studies. Students' self-efficacy is the confidence that they can successfully engage in enterprenuerial behaviour which stems from their capabilities and skills. This indicated that enterprenuerial education did not contribute to enhancing students' enterprenuerial competences. This implied that a deficiency in the design of curriculum which did not tackle the necessary topics to equip them with the necessary skills.

Recommendations

This study therefore recommends that:

- i. Kano State government should incorporate enterprenuership education at all levels of educational system viz. primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions in the State. This will boost the morale and capacities for the student's participation in enterprenuership activities;
- ii. The local government councils of the State and stakeholders such as voluntary individual, NGOs, and multinational co-operations should be given the authority to established adequate skill acquisition centres in their various communities in the State as a gesture for cooperate social responsibility, and
- iii. The National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) should embrace the spirit of enterprenuership and skill acquisition among the teeming unemployed youths in Nigeria.

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